

INVESTIGATION OF FIBER-MATRIX BONDING BY MEANS
OF SINGLE-FILAMENT FRAGMENTATION TEST
AND A COMPUTER SIMULATION PROCEDURE

by

D.Karagiannis, E.Kyriakakis and G.C.Papanicolaou*

University of Patras
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Section of Applied Mechanics
Composite Materials Group
Patras 26500, GREECE

A B S T R A C T

Multiple fracture of fiber in a series of single-filament composite specimens was studied experimentally and by means of a computer simulation program. Microscale 30mm gauge length "dogbone" resin specimens with single fibers embedded through the length of the specimen have been studied in order to determine the degree of fiber-matrix bonding. The specimens are pulled in tension until the fiber fragments to a critical length. The number of fragments, the length of segments, the critical fiber length, the stress distribution around each one of the fragments as well as the dependence of these parameters on the externally applied load can be predicted by means of a computer simulation program. A series of different materials combinations have been used in order to correlate theoretical predictions with experimental findings.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastics have emerged as useful engineering materials. The main advantages of these materials are the high strength, high modulus and light weight. Their overall performance depends on a great number of parameters such as fibre damage, uniformity of fibre distribution and alignment. However, the most important of these parameters is the fibre-matrix interface.

In any fibre-reinforced material with fiber axes parallel to the direction of loading, the load transfer from matrix to fiber is through interfacial shear actions. Consequently, the structure and the properties of the fibre-matrix interface play a major role in the physico-mechanical properties of composite materials. For example, a strong interface results in an increase in composite's strength while impact strength

* To whom all correspondence should be addressed.

and toughness may be reduced [1]. In contrary, a weak interface may result in an increase in fracture toughness.

The interfacial region that exists between fibers and matrix is not infinitesimally small in thickness; there is a region of finite thickness which is different in composition from both the fibers and matrix. Thus the region is not strictly an interface, and is nowadays referred to as the interphase [2-6].

A great number of experimental methods have been developed for the determination of the interfacial strength in fibre-reinforced composites. A popular method for measuring fiber-matrix adhesion is ILSS. The short-beam shear test is economically attractive with respect to specimen preparation and testing. However, it does not produce pure shear, because of bending of the beam and contact stressing at the points of support and loading [7].

Another popular experimental method is that the well-known pull-out test. According to this method, a single fiber is embedded into a polymer and the force required to pull it out is measured. However, problems such as clamping and alignment of the assembly as well as the degree of accuracy of measuring the embedded fiber length renders the method quite difficult [1].

Finally, the single-filament fragmentation test, although difficult to analyze, offers more information concerning interfacial behaviour. The model system consists of a single fibre embedded in a matrix under stress. The fragmentation test on single-fiber composite is suitable to measure directly the interfacial shear strength. A tensile load applied to the specimen, is transmitted from the matrix to the fiber and the fibre should break into fragments until a limiting fragment size, defining a critical length l_c , is reached.

Although fragmentation test is a relatively simple experimental method, the analysis of the results obtained depends on the specific fibre strength distribution considered. Thus, as it has been shown, a continuous visual observation of the fracture process is needed in order to provide insight into the type of adhesion present, while a special apparatus and technique for observing the fracture processes and fragment distribution has been developed [8].

In the present work the tensile behaviour of single carbon and/or glass fiber-epoxy matrix composites was investigated by means of a two-dimensional computer simulation procedure. The method applied in the present paper is based on a similar work developed by Ochiai and Osamura [9] for the case of metal-matrix composites. Respective experimental results are well described by the present computer simulation.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

All specimens had an epoxy matrix of the type Ciba-Geigy XB 3052 A. The hardener used was of the type Ciba-Geigy XB 3052 B.

Two different types of fibres were applied. Namely, a carbon fibre type T-300 ($5\mu\text{m}$ nominal diameter) and a single mode optical fiber consisted of a silica based core and a cladding protected by an acrylate coating.

The tensile strength of the carbon fibers was 2300 MPa, the tensile modulus was 230 GPa, and the elongation at break 1%.

The glass fiber had a core of $50\mu\text{m}$, the cladding diameter was approximately $125\mu\text{m}$ and combined with the coating the overall diameter was approximately $250\mu\text{m}$. The inner layer, called the primary coating, was typically a soft (low cross-link density - low modulus) urethane acrylate, designed to buffer the glass fiber mechanically against microbending. The outer layer, called the secondary coating, is a hard (high cross-link density) epoxy acrylate designed to protect the glass fiber against mechanical abrasion and other adverse mechanical, thermal, and chemical environments.

Dogbone single - filament specimens (Fig.1) were prepared by using a silicone - rubber mould. The epoxy and hardener were mixed at room temperature and stirred thoroughly to form a homogeneous mixture. The mixing ratio applied was 100/38 by weight and the mixture was degassed under vacuum for 20'. The fiber was suspended in the empty mold at the cavity center lines which helped to keep the fiber centered at the half thickness of the cavity. The epoxy matrix was then heated at 40°C for a couple of minutes and the hot mixture was subsequently slowly casted into the silicone mould. Finally, the whole system was cured for 20hrs at 50°C . The thus prepared composite specimens were tested under tension by means of an Instron-type testing machine. The cross-head speed applied was $0.5\text{mm}/\text{min}$.

Figure 1. Single-filament specimen's geometry

3. THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

In the present work a modified theoretical model based on the Ochiai-Osamura [9] model was adopted. The basic assumptions of the modified model are: a) The matrix material is characterized by a linear elastic-plastic behaviour, b) Shrinkage and residual stresses are neglected, c) Radial and hoop stresses are neglected, d) A stress-strain behaviour of the matrix material of the type shown in Fig.2 has been adopted, e) A linear elastic behaviour of the fibre has been assumed.

Figure 2. Assumed stress-strain behaviour of the matrix

The above-mentioned assumptions differ from those of the Ochiai-Osamura model in that the present model is more simplified taking into account only three stages of matrix deformation instead of the numerous stages considered in the Ochiai model. The fibre always deforms in a linear elastic way, while plastic deformation in shear is not taken into account.

A schematic representation of the one fibre-model composite is shown in Fig.3. For each one of the fragments created during the tensile test of the one-fibre composite, the following mechanism has been assumed: When the load is applied both fibre and matrix deform in a linear elastic way (stage A, Fig.4a). With increasing the load level, the matrix becomes plastic in tension while the fibre deforms elastically (stage B, Fig.4b). With further increasing load, the plastic deformation of the matrix in tension increases until the whole of the matrix material becomes plastic (stage C, Fig.4c). This mechanism constitutes a small part of the whole mechanism proposed in [9].

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the model

Figure 4. Deformation stages

In order to determine the stress distribution in matrix and fibre, the Ochiai-Osamura model [9] originally developed for the case of metal-matrix composites, has been modified and applied.

Next, a computer simulation on the multiple fracture of the composite specimens under investigation was carried out. The strength of the elements was determined using Monte-Carlo method. Two different fiber-strength distributions were adopted. Namely, a Weibull distribution which provides the probability P of failure at stress σ as

$$P = 1 - \exp[-V \{(\sigma - \sigma_u)/\sigma_o\}^m]$$

where m is the Weibull modulus, V is the volume of the material, σ_o is the normalizing factor and σ_u is the stress below which there is no probability of failure taken in all cases equal to zero; and a Sigma distribution which provides the same probability as:

$$P = 1 - \exp [-A \{1 - e^{-(\sigma - \sigma_u/\sigma_o)^m}\}]$$

where A is the total number of defects per unit length.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Figures 5 and 6 show photomicrographs of the fractured carbon-epoxy and optical fibre-epoxy one-filament composites respectively.

Figure 5. Carbon-epoxy

Figure 6. Optical fiber-epoxy

The normal and shear stress distributions along each one of the fragments for the carbon - epoxy specimens as derived from the analytical model are given in figures 7 and 8 respectively.

Figure 7. Normal stress distribution

Figure 8. Shear stress distribution

Next, a comparison between the predicted fragment-and length distribution when considering Sigma and Weibull functions is illustrated in Figures 9 and 10 respectively.

FRAGMENT DISTRIBUTION

Figure 9. Sigma function

FRAGMENT DISTRIBUTION

Figure 10. Weibull function

It has been observed that Sigma function agree well with respective experimental findings, while Weibull function gives some deviates.

Normal and shear stress distribution along the frangments for the optical fiber composites are given in Figures 11 and 12.

Figure 11. Normal stress distribution

Figure 12. Shear stress distribution

Finally, for the optical fiber-epoxy composites, the fragment length distribution when applying the Weibull function is shown in Fig.13. This distribution correlates well with experimental findings.

Figure 13. Fragment length distribution for the optical fiber-epoxy specimens.

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